

Spectroscopic Methods of Determining Equilibrium Constant and Molar Absorbance of Charge-transfer Complexes

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The birth of quantum mechanics has no doubt unravelled the nature of chemical bonds in molecules in both qualitative and quantitative terms; but as more and more new and interesting chemical phenomena are being probed, the enigmatic nature of the valency problem becomes apparent. This is illustrated by organic molecular complexes, particularly those of the charge-transfer type which are formed by interaction between apparently saturated neutral organic molecules such as the benzene-chloranil complex. CT-complexes have attracted the attention of chemists, biologists and physicists for their new and interesting properties which are normally absent in the components of the complex. Although organic molecular complexes of the charge-transfer type are known for a pretty long time, yet it is only in the fifties that a systematic research on them has started. Many of these complexes have been isolated in the solid state while others exist only in solution in which they are in equilibrium with their components.

IN 1948 Benesi and Hildebrand¹ suggested a suitable spectrophotometric method for determining the equilibrium constant and extinction coefficient of the complexes in solution. This method coupled with Mulliken's² formulation of these complexes as of the charge-transfer type has given a tremendous impetus to researches in this area. Since then phenomenal progress has been made in the equilibrium studies of these complexes in solution and more recently in gas phase. The purpose of the present work is to review the spectrophotometric methods of studying the equilibria of molecular complex formation reactions, to list the various modifications of Benesi-Hildebrand equation together with a discussion of their relative merits and demerits. The present review includes the nmr method of determining equilibrium constant of CT-complexes as this versatile technique is being increasingly used by different workers engaged in this area of research.

Benesi-Hildebrand Equation :

A survey of the vast literature already accumulated on organic CT-complexes reveals that in solution 1:1 type complexes are formed in most cases. However, evidence³ is gradually accumulating on the existence of higher order complexes in solution. The equilibrium constant for a 1:1 complex formed according to the reaction (1)

where A, D and DA represent the acceptor, donor and the complex respectively, is given by the relation

$$K = \frac{C_{DA}}{C_A C_D} = \frac{C_{DA}}{(C_A^0 - C_{DA})(C_D^0 - C_{DA})} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where C's refer to the concentrations of the various species in equilibrium, C_A^0 and C_D^0 are the initial concentrations of the acceptor and the donor respectively. In most cases the concentrations are expressed in moles per litre when K is designated K_C and has the units of litre per mole ($l\text{m}^{-1}$). If concentrations are expressed in mole fractions then K is designated K_X or K_N . The equilibrium constant K_C is often called the association or stability constant.

Various methods are available for the determination of K of molecular complexes in solution. They can be broadly divided into two groups: (a) Spectroscopic methods and (b) Non-spectral methods. The present article confines itself to a critical review of the spectroscopic methods of evaluating the equilibrium constant and other relevant parameters of organic CT-complexes in solution. The first successful spectroscopic method of determining K and other related parameters was worked out by Benesi and Hildebrand (loc. cit) whose pioneering work in conjunction with Mulliken's formulation of organic molecular complexes as charge-transfer complexes opened the

flood gate of researches into the solution chemistry of the complexes concerned.

The underlying principle of spectroscopic determination of 'K' of complexes in solution is that the absorption spectrum of a solution containing a donor-acceptor complex often is markedly different from the composite spectra of the free donor and the acceptor or the formation of DA is accompanied by a shift in the absorption maxima or nmr line position of either the donor or the acceptor or both. Customarily molecular complexes are studied under conditions in which the concentration of one of the components (usually the donor) is varied systematically and is used in much greater excess of the other (commonly the acceptor) whose concentration is kept fixed at a low level. This condition ensures that one of the partners of donor-acceptor complex is appreciably complexed.

Under the experimental conditions mentioned the equation (2) reduces to (3)

$$K = \frac{C_{DA}}{(C_A^0 - C_{DA}) C_D^0} \quad \dots (3)$$

from which Benesi and Hildebrand (loc. cit.) deduced their now famous equation(4)

$$\frac{C_A^0 1}{d} = \frac{1}{K \epsilon_{DA} C_D^0} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{DA}} \quad \dots (4)$$

valid for $C_D^0 \gg C_A^0$ and that neither A nor D absorbs in the region of the charge-transfer band, l is the path length, d is the optical density of the solution

$(\log \frac{I_0}{I})$, ϵ_{DA} is the molar absorbance of the complex. The equation (4) demands that a plot of

$\frac{C_A^0 1}{d}$ versus $\frac{1}{C_D^0}$ should be linear with slope

$\frac{1}{K \epsilon_{DA}}$ and intercept $\frac{1}{\epsilon_{DA}}$. The equation (4) is the most popular method of evaluating K and ϵ_{DA} of organic EDA* complexes from spectrophotometric data.

The B-H equation (4) assumes that it is only the complex which absorbs at the wavelength of measurement, the absorbance of the components is negligible. A modification which does not involve this assumption has been suggested by Ketelaar⁴ who proposed the following equation (5)

$$\frac{C_A^0 1}{d - d_A^0} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A) C_D^0} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A} \quad \dots (5)$$

where ϵ_A is the extinction coefficient of the acceptor, d_A^0 is the optical density of a solution containing

only the acceptor at a concentration C_A^0 , d is the optical density of the mixture containing the donor and the acceptor measured against the donor blank (an acceptor free solution which contains the donor at the same concentration as in the solution of the complex) as the reference. The equation (5) is sometimes written in the following form (6)

$$\frac{1}{\epsilon_a - \epsilon_A} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A) C_D^0} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A} \quad \dots (6)$$

where ϵ_a , the apparent extinction coefficient of the acceptor in the donor solution, is defined as

$$\epsilon_a = \frac{d}{C_A^0 l} \quad \dots (7)$$

According to equations (5) and (6) a plot of the left hand side versus $\frac{1}{C_D^0}$ should yield a straight

line in cases where they apply. The extinction coefficient of the complex is obtained from the intercept of this line, and the association is calculated from the combined slope and intercept. It is evident that Ketelaar's equation reduces to the B-H equation (4) when $\epsilon_A = 0$.

A critical appraisal of B-H equation (4) or its modified form (5) has been made by Hammond⁵ who examined the effect of errors in measuring optical density, concentrations of the donor and the acceptor on plots of the following alternative forms of (4) or (5) including obviously the original forms of B-H and Ketelaar equations :

$$\frac{C_A^0 C_D^0 1}{d - d_A^0} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A)} + \frac{C_D^0}{(\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A)} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\frac{C_D^0 1}{d - d_A^0} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A) C_A^0} + \frac{C_D^0}{(\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A) C_A^0} \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\frac{1}{d - d_A^0} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A) C_A^0 C_D^0} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A) C_A^0} \quad \dots (10)$$

It was noted that of the equations (4) or (5), (8), (9) and (10) the equations (8) and (9) in particular, although they afforded satisfactory plots for stronger acceptors, gave marked scatter for systems with low values of K (< 1). It was noted that scatter of points about a straight line depends on the binding strength (K) of the donor-acceptor complex, and whether the relation is expressed as (4) or (5), (8), (9) and (10). The relations (8) and (9) show a complementary effect on the scatter of experimental points. Whereas one of these forms produces scatter only at low values of K , the other does so only at large K . Hammond (loc. cit.) has recommended the use of equation (10) in general since scatter in points arises from errors in C_D^0 and $d - d_A^0$ alone.

*EDA—electron donor-acceptor.

The equation (8) is known as the Benesi-Hildebrand-Scott⁶ equation which differs from the equations (4) or (5) in that it extrapolates through a region of decreasing concentration, i.e., decreasing absorbance so that percentage errors are greater than that found in the case of equations (4) and (5). Experience has shown that for the same set of experimental data while B-H equation (4) or its modified form Ketelaar equation (5) gives a linear plot of LHS vs the reciprocal of donor concentration, the ordinate values in the Scott's equation (8) show fluctuations with concentration of donor.

The following rearranged form of B-H equation (11) is frequently used⁷ to evaluate the equilibrium constant and extinction coefficient of the complex

$$\frac{d}{C_D^0} = -Kd + KC_A^0 \epsilon_{DA} \quad \dots (11)$$

According to equation (11) a plot of d/C_D^0 against d should be linear with a gradient equal to $-K$ and the intercept extrapolated to infinitely dilute solution yields ϵ_{DA} . The equation (11) may be written in the following form (12)

$$\frac{\epsilon_a}{C_D^0} = -K\epsilon_a + K\epsilon_{DA} \quad \dots (12)$$

Ketelaar's equation (5) or (6) may be used in forms corresponding to equations (11) and (12).

Rose-Drago Equation :

With progress in the studies of equilibria involving the formation of molecular complexes the limitations of the B-H and Ketelaar methods have been felt and attempts were made to derive new equations of which the most noteworthy is the Rose-Drago equation⁸(13) (henceforth abbreviated as R-D equation) which is claimed to be perfectly general and gives the B-H and Ketelaar equations as special cases. For 1 : 1 type complex and when measurements are made against the donor blank as reference the R-D equation is

$$K^{-1} = \frac{(d-d_A^0)}{I(\epsilon_{DA}-\epsilon_A)} - (C_A^0 + C_D^0) + \frac{1}{(d-d_A^0)} C_D^0 C_A^0 (\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A) \quad \dots (13)$$

For measurements carried out against the solvent blank as the reference the equation (13) takes the form (13a).

$$K^{-1} = \frac{(d-d_A^0-d_D^0)}{I(\epsilon_{DA}-\epsilon_A-\epsilon_D)} - (C_A^0 + C_D^0) + \frac{1}{(d-d_A^0-d_D^0)} C_D^0 C_A^0 (\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D) \quad \dots (13a)$$

The various terms in equations(13)and(13a)have their usual significance. An analytical solution for ϵ_{DA} could be obtained by constructing two simultaneous equations each representing different experimental trials. However, Rose and Drago (loc.cit.) developed an alternative and at the same time more convenient graphical procedure for solving their equation. Their method consists in random selection of ϵ_{DA} values and calculation of K^{-1} from one set of experimental data, namely, initial concentrations of donor and acceptor, plotting K^{-1} as a function of ϵ_0 , repetition of this procedure with other sets, and finally evaluating K^{-1} and ϵ_0 values from the common point of intersection. The equation (13) or (13a)has been tested with many different systems such as benzene-iodine in carbon tetrachloride, the trimethylamine-iodine, biphenyl-iodine, dioxane-iodine and hexaethyl benzene-iodine interactions⁹. The equation is claimed to be superior to the Benesi-Hildebrand relation (4) and Ketelaar's equation (5), since it does not assume completion of the donor acceptor interactions and it caters for nearly all cases, such as band overlap or where the extinction coefficient of the complex is a constant independent of the base concentration and the bulk dielectric constant of the solvent.

The method developed by Rose and Drago for solving their equation (13) or (13a) demands an intuitive guess of ϵ_{DA} values. But selection of ϵ_{DA} values at random and that too for each set of experimental data, renders their graphical method laborious and sometimes more difficult to apply. In many cases R-D plots show a wide scatter in the values of K and ϵ_{DA} evaluated. Alternatively Seal *et al.*¹⁰ have developed a graphical procedure by expressing the R-D equation (13) in the following form

$$y = L + Mx - M^2Z \quad \dots (14)$$

$$\text{where } y = \frac{1C_A^0C_D^0}{d-d_A^0}, \quad x = C_A^0 + C_D^0, \quad Z = \frac{d-d_A^0}{1}$$

$$L = \frac{K^{-1}}{\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A} \quad \text{and} \quad M = \frac{1}{\epsilon_{DA} - \epsilon_A}$$

From definitions and experimental conditions it can be shown that Z is a linear function of C_{DA} which again is a linear function of x . Thus, substitution of $Z = mx + C$ in equation (14) gives

$$y = L - M^2C + (M - M^2m)x \quad \dots (15)$$

which yields a linear plot of y vs x with slope $S = (M - M^2m) \dots (16)$ and intercept $I = L - M^2C \dots (17)$. Substituting the admissible value of $M = (1 - \sqrt{1-4mS})/2m$ in (17) one gets L and finally $K = \frac{M}{L}$ and $\epsilon_{DA} = M^{-1} + \epsilon_A$

This alternative graphical method which has been tested¹⁰ with a variety of systems yields results comparable to those obtained by iterative procedure.

Nagakura's Equation :

Nagakura¹¹ proposed the use of equation (18) for determination of the stability constant, K_o , of molecular complexes in solution

$$K_o = \frac{[C_D(k_o - k') + C'_D(k - k_o)]}{[C_D C'_D(k' - k)]} \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

where k_o , k and k' are the absorbances, measured at a fixed wavelength, of solutions in which the concentrations of the acceptor are equal and concentrations of donor are O , C_D and C'_D respectively. This method has the advantage in that the effect of superposed absorption belonging to either of the components is considered explicitly in this equation. Another advantage of this equation is that the equilibrium constant can be obtained independently of the molar extinction coefficient of the complex. The equation (18) is valid under Benesi-Hildebrand conditions, i.e., $C_D^o \gg C_A^o$.

Recently Seal *et al.*¹² have developed general analytical procedures for calculating K and ϵ_{DA} of organic molecular complexes independently of each other from spectrophotometric data. They proposed the use of the following equations for the purpose :

$$aK^3 + bK^2 + gK + h = 0 \quad \dots \quad (19)$$

$$\text{and } ml^2 \epsilon_{DA}^2 - nl \epsilon_{DA} + f = 0 \quad \dots \quad (20)$$

The equation(19) is cubic in K and does not contain ϵ , while(20) is quadratic in ϵ_{DA} and is independent of K . The various coefficients in equations (19) and (20) are functions of experimental quantities. The equations have been tested using literature data on a large number of widely different systems. The agreement between the values of K and ϵ_{DA} determined by using this procedure and those obtained by other well-known methods is fairly good in most of the systems studied.

Equimolar Method :

Equilibrium studies on molecular complexes in solution are normally carried out under non-equimolar conditions in which the concentration of the acceptor is usually kept fixed, that of the donor is varied and is used in much greater excess of the acceptor. One reason for using the non-equimolar method is the low solubility, particularly, of the acceptor in most cases. The other reason is the working of the law of mass action whereby a larger fraction of one component is in the complexed state. In cases where there is no solubility restriction of the reacting partners the equimolar method of determining the association constant should preferably be used since the errors involved in the evaluation of K and ϵ_{DA} by this procedure is the least. The method has been used by several workers¹³, particularly by Foster and his group¹⁴

who employed the following equation for the purpose

$$\frac{C_A^o l}{d} = \frac{(K \epsilon_{DA})^{-1}}{C_A^o} + \frac{2}{\epsilon_{DA}} \quad \dots \quad (21)$$

The formation of 1 : 1 type complex (than other types) is more favourable under equimolar condition than under non-equimolar situations. Foster *et al.*¹⁴ have shown that minimum deviation from Beer's law for a given measurable concentration of 1 : 1 complex would occur only when the total solute concentration is minimum, i.e., under the condition $[D]=[A]$ where the square brackets denote concentration. It can be shown¹⁵ by simple calculation that by keeping the total solute concentration a minimum a larger concentration of the complex with 1 : 1 stoichiometry can be obtained under equimolar condition than under non-equimolar situations. According to Person¹⁵, it is under such a condition that a better value of the formation constant can be obtained.

Simultaneous Determination of Absolute Composition and Equilibrium Constant :

Foster⁷ has developed a method for the simultaneous determination of absolute composition and association constant of molecular complexes having 1 : n stoichiometry. The association constant, K , of a complex, AD_n , at high concentration of the donor, is

$$K = \frac{C_{DA}}{(C_A^o - C_{DA})C_D^{on}} \quad \dots \quad (22)$$

Assuming that the extinction coefficients of the donor and acceptor are negligible at the wavelength of measurement and substituting the appropriate optical parameters the equation (22) becomes

$$\frac{d}{C_D^{on}} = KC_A^o \epsilon_{DA} - Kd \quad \dots \quad (23)$$

where d is the optical density of the solution containing the complex, free donor and free acceptor respectively. The equation (23) shows that a plot of $\frac{d}{C_D^{on}}$ against d should be linear, the gradient being equal to $-K$, the intercept with the x -axis being $KC_A^o \epsilon_{DA}$. The method has been applied to the study of interactions between S-TNB and (i) diphenyl amine, (ii) dimethyl amine.

Displacement Method :

A displacement method involving a spectrophotometric evaluation of equilibrium constants of molecular complexes was proposed by Foster¹⁶. In this method the association constant of a complex AB' is determined by studying the diminution in

the intensity of absorption of another complex AB'' which alone absorbs at the wavelength of measurement. The procedure is to study simultaneously the following equilibria

where B' and B'' represent a pair of Lewis bases which complete simultaneously with a Lewis acid A (1 : 1 interaction is assumed). The equilibrium constant K' of the reaction (24) is obtained from the following equation (26)

$$K = \frac{D_0 - D_1}{D_1} \frac{(1 + C_{B''}^0 K'')}{C_{B'}^0} \quad \dots \quad (26)$$

where D₀ is the optical density of a solution containing A at a concentration C_A⁰ and B'' at a concentration C_{B''}⁰, but containing no B'; D₁ is the optical density of a solution containing A and B'' at a concentration C_A⁰ and C_{B''}⁰ and B' at a concentration C_{B'}⁰. The equation (26) is valid under conditions C_{B'}⁰ ≫ C_A⁰ and C_{B''}⁰ ≫ C_A⁰. Thus if K' is known a value of K'' may be calculated. The method has been applied for evaluating association constants for the equilibria between N-alkyl anilines and chloranil. This competitive method is similar to that of Ostwald's method for finding acid strength by allowing two acids to compete for a single base.

Dilution Method :

A dilution method based on the equation (27) has been devised by Foster, Hammick and Wardley¹⁷ to determine K and ε_{DA} of the complex

$$v = \frac{K \epsilon_{DA} m_A m_D}{vd} - K m_D \quad \dots \quad (27)$$

where m_A and m_D are the mole masses of the acceptor and the donor respectively and v is the volume of the solution in litres. The equation is valid for Benesi-Hildebrand condition and a plot of v against (vd)⁻¹ should be linear.

Determination of Association Constant from Emission Spectra :

Most organic charge-transfer complexes do not normally fluoresce. When the acceptor or the donor or both are fluorescent, CT-complex formation is usually accompanied by a reduction in the intensity of fluorescence of the components. The efficiency of the quenching process is governed by the efficiency of the ground-state complex formation :

This fact can be utilized for measuring the association constant of the complex by using the Stern-Volmer equation (28).

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_0 C_D^0 \quad \dots \quad (28)$$

Where F⁰ is the quantum yield of fluorescence of A alone in the absence of the non-fluorescent quencher D, F is that of A in the presence of D at a concentration C_D⁰. According to equation (28) a plot

of $\frac{F_0}{F}$ versus C_D⁰ should give the association

constant K₀. Many studies on charge-transfer fluorescence show that there is good agreement between K₀ of the Stern-Volmer equation and that obtained by the B-H method, although discrepancies are also observed.

Experience with works on organic CT-complexes has shown that for strong molecular complexes the values of K and ε_{DA} obtained by different workers show good agreement in constancy; but for weak molecular complexes the reported values of these parameters show wide departures from each other. Due to the reported anomalies in the values of K and ε in the case of weak molecular complexes their existence has been questioned. Several authors have pointed out that the observed discrepancies in the values of K and ε_{DA} may be due to one or more of the following reasons: (i) the existence of higher-order complexes, (ii) dimerisation of the component present in excess, (iii) the presence in solution of contact complexes, (iv) solvent interactions, (v) non-ideality of the solution, etc.

Higher Order Complexes :

Studies on a large number of organic EDA complexes have revealed that in most cases complexes formed are of the type 1 : 1. Evidence, however, is gradually accumulating on the existence in solution of higher order complexes. Johnson and Bowen¹⁸ have shown as a result of investigations concerning a number of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 complexes that the criterion of linearity of B-H plots indicating the presence of only stable 1 : 1 CT-complexes and/or contact species is not a valid one. These authors have claimed that under certain conditions straight lines are apparently obtained according to the B-H equation even when the stoichiometry is not 1 : 1. When two complexes of different stoichiometry, e.g., AD and AD₂ or A₂D are simultaneously present in solution the following equation (30) relating the equilibrium constants of the reactions (29a) and (29b) may be derived

$$\frac{C_D^0}{\epsilon - \epsilon_0} = \frac{1 + K_1 C_D^0 + K_2 C_D^{02}}{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_0) K_1 + (\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_0) K_2 C_D^0} \quad \dots (30)$$

The derivation of equation (30) makes use of the adequate approximation $C_D^0 \gg C_A^0$. The use of equation (30) to determine the equilibrium constants and extinction coefficients is based on the approximation that these quantities are independent of the concentration of the donor. In equation (30) ϵ is the formal extinction coefficient of a solution containing an initial concentration of the acceptor C_A^0 moles litre⁻¹, ϵ_0 is the molar extinction coefficient of the acceptor at the same wavelength, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the molar extinction coefficients of 1:1 and 2:1 complexes respectively. Foster¹⁹ derived the following equation (31)

$$\frac{d}{C_A^0 C_D^0 I} = - \left(\frac{dk_1}{C_A^0 I} \right) (1 + K_2 C_D^0) + K_1 (\epsilon_1 + K_2 \epsilon_2 C_D^0) \quad \dots \quad (31)$$

for use in the optical measurements when complexes of the types AD and AD₂ are present simultaneously in solution. In equation (31) K₂ is the equilibrium constant of the reaction (32)

A special computer programme has been written by Foster¹⁹ in order to calculate the best values of the parameters K₁, K₂, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 of the complexes mentioned above. The equation (31) is valid under the condition when $C_D^0 \gg C_A^0$. The equation (31) may be written into the Bensi-Hildebrand and Scott forms.

Self-Association and Equilibrium Constant :

One of the many explanations that have been suggested to account for the deviations from the B-H or related equations is the possible self-association of one or more solute species and its effect on the spectrophotometric determination of association constants. For the most likely case in solutions where $C_D^0 \gg C_A^0$ in which A and AD absorb optically and D dimerises, the measured K is

$$K_{\text{measured}} = K (1 + 2K_2 C_D)^{-1} \quad \dots \quad (33)$$

where K₂ is the dimerisation constant C_{D_2} / C_D^2 for the donor, $K = \frac{C_{AD}}{(C_A^0 - C_{AD}) C_D}$ and $K_{\text{measured}} = \frac{C_{AD}}{(C_A^0 - C_{AD}) C_D^2}$.

With many combinations of synthetic input parameters like extinction coefficients, association constants

and self-association constants Tanner and Bruce²⁰ observed that the curvature of a Benesi-Hildebrand plot is not large except for very large values of dimerisation constant. The equation (33) assumes that the dimer does not interact with A.

Contact Complexes :

Mulliken's (loc. cit.) theory of CT-complexes and their spectra predicts that there should in general be a relationship between the stability of the complex and the intensity of CT-bands; the stronger the complex, the more intense should be the bands. In reality an inverse relationship between these quantities is more commonly observed²¹, and, for some very weak complexes very high extinction coefficients have been observed²¹. The B-H equation seems not to apply to very weak complexes. For example, a solution of iodine in perfluoroheptane does not show any significant absorption beyond wavelengths greater than 200 nm, but when n-heptane is added to solutions of iodine in perfluoroheptane, extended absorption to a wavelength of about 260 nm occurs, and the intensity of this new absorption increases strictly linearly with n-heptane concentration. For the system mentioned above it has been found that a B-H plot gives a straight line passing through the origin, which means that $\epsilon_{\text{complex}}$ is infinity, and $K = 0$. An explanation for this apparent enigma was put forward by Mulliken and Orgel²² who suggested that there are two types of charge-transfer absorption, one associated with real complexes which satisfy the mass-action law, and the other with DA pairs which happen to be together just through collisions. In order to make B-H equation applicable to very weak complexes in which interchange of electrons accompanies random encounters of donors and acceptors Mulliken and Orgel (loc. cit.) suggested the following equation (34)

$$\frac{C_A^0 I}{O.D.} = \frac{1}{\alpha' \epsilon_{DA}} \frac{1}{C_D^0} \quad \dots \quad (34)$$

where α' is the number of sites for a donor molecule around any acceptor molecule. The equation (34) is valid for pure contact absorption.

Mulliken and Orgel (loc. cit.) have considered situations in which the total absorption is due to a mixture of bound and contact complexes for which they have suggested the following equation (35)

$$\frac{C_A^0 I}{O.D.} = \frac{1}{K \epsilon_{\text{eff}}} \frac{1}{C_D^0} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{\text{eff}}} \quad \dots \quad (35)$$

where $\epsilon_{\text{eff}} = \epsilon_{DA} + \frac{\alpha' C_{DA}}{K}$ and is the measured extinction coefficient.

Solvent Interactions :

Carter, Murrell and Rosch²³ pointed out that

Mulliken-Orgel theory has two unsatisfactory features of which the assumption regarding the existence of two kinds of complex, one obeying the law of mass action and the other not, cannot be thermodynamically justified; secondly, the involvement of the solvent in the charge-transfer interactions has not been considered in their theory. In the case of weak complexes the solvent is competing with the donor for the sites around the acceptor, a belief that has been experimentally substantiated by the observations²⁴ that K depends on the solvent. These authors have argued that if the competition between complexing and solvation is allowed for in theory, there is no need to invoke the concept of two kinds of complex, real and contact, and the behaviour of weak complexes can be fitted into the same theory as is that of the strong complexes. On this basis they have derived the following equation (36)

$$\frac{C_A^0 I}{d} = \frac{1}{C_D^0} \frac{x_s^q}{K \epsilon_{DA}} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{DA}} \quad \dots \quad (36)$$

where x_s is the concentration of the free solvent in mole-fraction defined relative to the total number of moles of D, A, and S (complexed and uncomplexed). The equilibrium constant K which represents the equilibrium

is given by

$$K = \frac{[C] x_s^q}{[AS_n][DS_m]} \quad \dots \quad (38)$$

where S stands for the solvent and $q = n + m - p$. All other symbols have their usual significance. The equation (36) differs from the B-H equation (4) only by the inclusion of the mole fraction of free solvent. The relation between this equilibrium constant and the one from the Benesi-Hildebrand equation is given by

$$K_{B-H} = K - \frac{q(m+1)}{S_0} \quad \dots \quad (39)$$

where S_0 is the total concentration of the solvent in the absence of the donor.

$$\epsilon_{B-H} = \epsilon_0 \left(\frac{K}{K_{B-H}} \right) \quad \dots \quad (40)$$

From (39) it appears that the B-H method does not measure true K ; rather it underestimates K by an amount $\frac{q(m+1)}{S_0}$. Similarly, from (40) it is clear

that a B-H analysis overestimates ϵ_0 by the ratio K/K_{B-H} . For strong complexes, $K \gg q(m+1)/S_0$ and the B-H analysis is valid.

Carter, Murrell and Rosch (loc. cit.) verified their theory by noting that for a series of related complexes a plot of ϵ vs K corrected for by using an optimal value of $q(m+1)$ gave a straight line with a positive slope and passed through the origin as demanded by Mulliken's theory. For the same complexes no such correlation was found for the uncorrected values of ϵ and K . Many criticisms for and against the theory of Carter, Murrell and Rosch have been made. The prediction of the theory that the product $K\epsilon$ for a complex in solution should be equal to that in the gas phase does not agree with observations²⁵. The theory also fails to account for the difference in optical and nmr values for K^{26} , and the relative constancy of ϵ_{BH} for some complexes in different solvents.^{26,27} However, Carter²⁸ has rejected the first of these criticisms on the ground that it is caused by higher-order complexes, and the second by pointing out that strong complexes do not require solvation correction. Although Scott^{29,30} has appreciated the value of the approach, other investigators^{31,32} find no improvement in ϵ vs K plots using the corrections mentioned above.

Many other attempts have been made on the role of complexation by the solvent in charge-transfer complexes. In these approaches the solvent has been viewed as a competitor for either or both the donor and the acceptor^{33,34}. For such competitive equilibria simplified by the assumption that only the donor and the acceptor are complexed by the solvent, it may be shown that

$$K_{c(corr)}^{AD} = K_{c(obs)}^{AD} (1 + K_c^{AS}[S]) (1 + K_c^{DS}[S]) \quad \dots \quad (41)$$

The large solvent dependence in K values for TCNE complexes observed by Merrifield and Philips³³ has been explained as due to solvent-acceptor complex formation. Trotter and Hanna³⁵ have approached the problem on more or less similar lines. Many³⁶ have attempted to determine directly the equilibrium constant for solvent-component complexation by using the relationship

$$K_{c(obs)}^{DA} = K_{c(corr)}^{DA} - K_c^{SD} K_{c(obs)}^{DA} [S]_0 \dots \dots \dots (42)$$

where $[S]_0$ is the concentration of interacting solvent. A plot of $K_{c(obs)}^{DA}$ vs $K_{c(obs)}^{DA} [S]_0$ gives both $K_{c(corr)}^{DA}$ and K_c^{SD} from the intercept and slope. Tamres³⁷ have extended the theory of Carter, Murrell and Rosch to higher order complexes.

Non-ideality of Solution :

In the determination of the equilibrium constant of organic molecular complexes in solution the activity coefficients of the various species in solution are often neglected. It has been shown by Mulliken and Person³⁸ that the neglect of solution non-ideality may lead to an overestimate of the extinction

coefficient of the complex in solution. Assuming that the thermodynamic equilibrium constant, K_a , is related to the measured one by

$$K_a = K \frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_A \gamma_D} = K \Gamma_i \quad \dots (43)$$

where γ terms refer to the activity coefficients of the various species in solution and Γ_i is the activity coefficient quotient on the appropriate concentration scale, and further assuming that Γ_i is a linear function of donor concentration (molar)

$$\Gamma_i = (1 + bc_D^0) \quad \dots (44)$$

Mulliken and Person³⁸ have shown that the B-H equation can be written as

$$\frac{C_A^0 l}{d} = \frac{1}{K_a \epsilon_0} \frac{1}{C_D^0} + \left(\frac{b}{K_a} + 1 \right) \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \quad \dots (45)$$

The relation between the true extinction coefficient ϵ_0 and the one derived by the Benesi-Hildebrand equation ϵ_{BH} is

$$\epsilon_{BH} = \frac{1}{(b/K_a + 1)} \epsilon_0 = \frac{K_a}{K_{BH}} \epsilon_0 \quad \dots (46)$$

Using regular solution theory³⁹ to estimate Γ_i , Mulliken and Person have shown that ϵ may be overestimated by as much as a factor of two for the benzene-iodine complex if activity coefficients are neglected.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Method :

The nmr technique has been applied to the study of equilibria involving the formation of molecular complexes. It is based on the shift of the nmr line position of a particular nucleus (or nuclei) in either the acceptor or the donor when complexation occurs. Use has been made of the following equation (47)

$$P_{AD} = \frac{\delta}{\Delta_{AD}^0} - \frac{\delta_A}{\Delta_{AD}^0} \quad \dots (47)$$

according to which a plot of P_{AD} (the fraction of complexed acceptor molecules) against δ (the measured shift) should be linear ;

$\Delta_{AD}^0 = \delta_{AD} - \delta_A$ is the shift for the pure complex relative to the shift for the pure acceptor in solution, δ_A and δ_{AD} being the chemical shifts of a nucleus in the acceptor in the experimental situation in the isolated acceptor and in the pure complex respectively. The method requires the deployment of trial values of the equilibrium constant until a plot of the values of P_{AD} obtained from it against δ yields a straight line⁴⁰. The method is suitable for solution by computer methods^{41,42}. However, this method is not generally used. Instead, a Benesi-Hildebrand

type method based on the following equation (48) is frequently employed to evaluate equilibrium constant of 1 : 1 type organic CT-complexes from nmr data.

$$\frac{1}{\Delta_{obs}} = \frac{1}{K \Delta_{AD}^0} \frac{1}{C_D^0} + \frac{1}{\Delta_{AD}^0} \quad \dots (48)$$

where $\Delta_{obs} = \delta_{obs} - \delta_A$. The equation (48) is the nmr analogue of the Benesi-Hildebrand equation for optical absorption and is valid under the situation in which $C_D^0 \gg C_A^0$. According to the equation (48) a plot of $1/\Delta_{obs}$ against $1/C_D^0$ should be linear with a gradient equal to $1/K \Delta_{AD}^0$ and intercept $1/\Delta_{AD}^0$ from which K and shift of the pure complex are calculated. Hanna and Ashbaugh⁴³ were the first to apply the equation (48) to a truly charge-transfer system. This equation suffers from the same type of disadvantages which are shared by its optical counterparts, viz., equation (4) or (5). To evaluate K it requires extrapolation to infinitely concentrated solution whereby an intercept whose value is relatively small is obtained.

Foster and Fyfe⁴⁴ employed the following equation (49)

$$\frac{\Delta}{C_D^0} = -K \Delta + K \Delta_{AD}^0 \quad \dots (49)$$

which is the nmr analogue of the optical equation (11). The equation (49) which is valid under B-H conditions, demands that a plot of Δ/C_D^0 against Δ should be a straight line whose gradient gives directly the value of $-K$ without recourse to an extrapolation to an infinitely concentrated solution as is required with the equation (48).

For solutions containing bimolecular and termolecular complexes the nmr counterpart of the optical equation (31) is

$$\frac{\Delta}{C_D^0} = -\Delta K_{AD} (1 + C_D^0 K_{AD,2}) + K_{AD} \{ \Delta_{AD}^0 + \Delta_{AD,2}^0 C_D^0 K_{AD,2} \} \dots (50)$$

where the various parameters have their usual significance. Extensive use of this equation was made by Foster *et al.*¹⁹ for the study of higher order complexes in solution. The equation (50) is valid under the condition $C_D^0 \gg C_A^0$. The nmr technique is being increasingly applied to the study of molecular complexes in solution. An excellent description of nuclear magnetic resonance as applied to the study of organic charge-transfer complexes is given by Foster²⁷.

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